

Advanced methyltriethoxysilane-modified silazane coating with enhanced durability and corrosion protection

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ABSTRACT

The present study aims to evaluate the effect of incorporating methyltriethoxysilane (MTES) into the Durazane 1800 backbone and to investigate how this modification influences the coating properties. The synthesis of MTES-modified polysilazane sols involved pre-hydrolysis of MTES via the sol-gel method, followed by its incorporation into the Durazane 1800 backbone. Furthermore, the modification of Durazane 1800 backbone involved the use of some catalysts such as tetra-*n*-butylammonium fluoride (TBAF) and dicumyl peroxide (DCP). Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) was employed to analyze the structural changes in the modified polysilazane. The most promising MTES-modified polysilazane sol was deposited as a coating on AISI 304 stainless steel, followed by heat treatment at 100 °C. FTIR analysis showed that the incorporation of MTES increased the cross-linking density and improved the curing of the polysilazane-derived network at low temperature. The MTES-modified polysilazane coatings have improved physical and chemical properties, including strong adhesion, high water contact angle (104°), and uniform thickness of 5 μm. Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) and polarization tests demonstrated excellent corrosion protection, with an impedance modulus of $1.34 \times 10^9 \Omega \cdot \text{cm}^2$ and a corrosion current density of $1 \times 10^{-10} \text{ A} \cdot \text{cm}^{-2}$, respectively. Additionally, the coatings showed strong chemical resistance to acidic and oxidative environments and effective self-cleaning performance.

1. Introduction

Traditional coatings based on organic polymers can be applied using simple painting techniques and are widely employed in decorative and protective applications. These coatings have excellent flexibility [1]. However, despite their accepted use, they require large amounts of raw material due to the need for thick layers. Also, they often have limited hardness and exhibit insufficient corrosion protection. As a result, developing thin coatings with improved hardness and high density remains a challenge for both industry and academia [2,3].

Polysilazane (PSZ), a Si-based polymer with a Si-N-Si backbone, has attracted considerable attention for its versatility, particularly for producing ceramic coatings by high-temperature pyrolysis ($T > 400 \text{ °C}$) [4,5]. Using this process, hard coatings characterized by high chemical resistance, thermal stability, and mechanical robustness can be produced, making them suitable for high temperature applications [6–8].

However, despite these advantages, the internal tensile stress associated with the polymer-to-ceramic transformation can cause crack formation, compromising its performance [9,10].

Polysilazane can also be cured at low temperature ($<100 \text{ °C}$) and in a humid atmosphere, due to the high reactivity of its Si-H and Si-NH-Si groups with water. In general, the polysilazanes can be classified into two main types: inorganic perhydropolysilazanes (PHPS) and organic-polysilazanes (OPSZ) [11]. While PHPS is the most widely used precursor for obtaining thin inorganic coatings ($<1 \text{ μm}$), OPSZ is preferred for producing thicker coatings ($\sim 10 \text{ μm}$) with ceramic-like hardness and polymer-like flexibility [12–14]. Nonetheless, the direct use of pure organic-polysilazanes (OPSZ), such as Durazane 1800, is not recommended for coating purposes, as it yields a poorly cross-linked coating with limited overall performance. Steric hindrance caused by the presence of bulky organic moieties in OPSZ, such as Si-CH₃ and Si-CH=CH₂ groups, limits the reactivity of Si-H and Si-NH-Si groups during the

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curing process, which in turn leads to coatings with a low degree of crosslinking. Modification of the OPSZ polymer by introducing organic molecules and employing catalysts such as ammonia, dicumyl peroxide (DCP), or tetrabutylammonium fluoride (TBAF) was therefore studied, not only to enhance the crosslinking degree but also to tailor properties of the polymer [10,13,15–19]. For example, Coan et al. [20] developed a hybrid polymeric coating introducing polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA) in the Durazane 1800 backbone using dicumyl peroxide (DCP) as a catalyst. The resulting coating showed enhanced thermal stability and improved adhesion, and corrosion properties compared to the pure polysilazane coating. Furtat et al. [16] prepared a fluorine-modified polysilazane coating by incorporating 2,2,2-trifluoroethanol (TFE) into the Durazane 1800 chain using tetra-n-butylammonium fluoride (TBAF) as a catalyst. This approach led to a coating with improved hydrophobicity and mechanical strength. Zhang et al. [21] employed α,ω -hydroxy silicone oil (HSO) to enhance the curing rate of Durazane 1033. The -OH group of the HSO molecule reacted with the Si-N/Si-H groups of OPSZ, facilitating its cross-linking and the formation of Si-O-Si bonds. At the same time, due to the lubricating behaviour of the silicone oil, the coating exhibited exceptional water sliding properties, making it suitable for applications requiring anti-icing and anti-sticking capabilities.

Recently, the incorporation of alkoxysilanes into the backbone of an OPSZ has emerged as a novel strategy to obtain cost-effective and easy-to-handle polysilazane coatings at low temperatures. For instance, Lo et al. [22] developed a fluorinated polysilazane (FPSZ) coating by grafting 1H,1H,2H,2H-perfluorodecyltrimethoxysilane (FAS-17) onto Durazane™ 1500RC via hydrolysis and condensation reactions. This coating enhanced the anti-icing properties of aluminium surfaces. On the other hand, Aruchamy et al. [23] worked on the synthesis of a novel formulation incorporating 3-glycidyoxypropyltrimethoxysilane (GPTMS) in the Durazane 1800 backbone. This modification resulted in a coating with improved corrosion and scratch resistance properties. Later, the same authors investigated how curing the GPTMS-modified OPSZ polymer under different relative humidity conditions affected the corrosion resistance of the coated stainless steel. Their findings demonstrated that a relative humidity of 40 % was required to obtain a dense polysilazane film with improved corrosion protection properties [24]. It is worth noting that while the inclusion of alkoxysilanes into polysilazane polymers allows the tuning of the coating properties, the modification of polysilazane with methyltriethoxysilane (MTES) has yet to be explored. Functionalizing the polysilazane backbone with MTES will introduce additional methyl groups (-CH₃) into the coating network, enhancing its hydrophobicity, durability, and corrosion protection [25].

The aim of the present study is to assess the effect of MTES incorporation into the Durazane 1800 backbone and to investigate how this modification influences the coating properties when applied to AISI 304 steel. The synthesis of the MTES-modified polysilazane involved a pre-hydrolysis step of MTES via the sol-gel method, followed by its incorporation into the Durazane 1800 backbone. The modification of the polysilazane backbone was studied by Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), while the corrosion protection performance of the coating was examined by electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) and polarization tests. Water contact angle measurements were also conducted to evaluate the hydrophobicity of the coating. Finally, additional tests were carried out to assess the chemical corrosion protection and self-cleaning properties of the resulting coating.

2. Experimental

2.1. Materials

Durazane™ 1800 (Merck, Germany), with the formula (-SiViMe-NH-)_{0.2}(-SiMeH-NH-)_{0.8}, was used as an organic polysilazane (OPSZ) precursor. Methyltriethoxysilane (MTES, Alfa Aesar, 98 %) was used as the alkoxysilane precursor. Nitric acid (65 %, Sigma Aldrich, Germany), Tetra-n-butylammonium fluoride (TBAF, 0.1 M in THF, Alfa Aesar,

Germany), and dicumyl peroxide (DCP, 98 %, Sigma Aldrich, Germany) were used as catalysts to promote the sol-gel reaction and the OPSZ crosslinking. Finally, n-butyl acetate (NBTA, 99.5 %, Sigma-Aldrich, Germany) was employed as a solvent. All the chemicals were used as received without further purification.

2.2. Synthesis and characterization of MTES-modified polysilazane

The MTES-modified polysilazane solution was prepared in three steps. A schematic representation of the synthesis route is shown in Fig. 1.

First, MTES was pre-hydrolyzed to promote partial hydrolysis of its alkoxide groups (Step 1). In this step, the effect of water and/or acid on the MTES hydrolysis reactions was evaluated. MTES was mixed with deionized water and maintained under continuous magnetic stirring at room temperature. Two molar ratios of water to MTES (H₂O/MTES: 0.1 and 0.8) were tested. The resulting sols were respectively labelled as HM1 and HM2. The addition of 0.02 g of concentrated nitric acid (HNO₃) to HM1 and HM2 sols and its effect on the hydrolysis reaction were also evaluated. These sols were respectively labelled as HM3 and HM4. Table 1 summarizes the composition of the four prepared sols.

In parallel, 8 g of Durazane™ 1800, previously dissolved in 9 g of n-butyl acetate, was mixed with 0.04 g of tetra-n-butylammonium fluoride (TBAF) (Step 2). After 30 min of stirring, the pre-hydrolyzed HM3 sol (Step 1) was incorporated dropwise into the pre-crosslinked Durazane™ 1800 solution (Step 2). Finally, in the Step 3, 0.24 g of dicumyl peroxide (DCP), dissolved in 3.7 g of n-butyl acetate (NBTA), was added to the solution obtained in the step 2. The final mixture was refluxed at 80 °C under continuous magnetic stirring for 4 h, and the final solution was labelled as HTDM. It should be mentioned that steps 2 and 3 were carried out under N₂ atmosphere in a standard Schlenk line to ensure inert environment and protect reaction mixtures from moisture or oxygen.

A solution without added MTES was prepared following the same procedure as described before. The resulting solution was referred to as HTD and was used to evaluate the effect of MTES addition in the Durazane 1800 backbone.

Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) (PerkinElmer Spectrum 100 spectrometer, PerkinElmer, Inc., Madrid, Spain) was used to monitor the reaction progress and analyze the polymer crosslinking behaviour. For the analysis, pure Durazane, HTD, and HTDM samples were heat-treated at 100 °C for 24 h. Spectra were recorded in the range from 4000 to 400 cm⁻¹ with a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹, using 8 scans per measurement. The viscosity of HTDM and HTD solutions was measured using a vibro-viscometer (AND Vibro, SV-1A). Each measurement was conducted in triplicate, and the average viscosity value was reported in mPa.s.

2.3. Deposition and characterization of coatings

The synthesized HTDM and HTD solutions were deposited on AISI 304 stainless steel substrates (25 mm × 65 mm; composition: 1.75 wt% Mn, 0.034 wt% Si, 17.71 wt% Cr, 8.23 wt% Ni, 0.021 wt% P, 0.009 wt% S, 0.07 wt% C, balance Fe) by dip-coating. Prior to deposition, the substrates were pre-cleaned using an alkaline solution (P3Emalan5668: P2Emalan0469, Miele, Germany).

The dipping process was carried out at 25 °C under 25–30 % relative humidity, using a withdrawal rate of 30 cm/min. The coated samples were heat-treated at 100 °C for 24 h. The final coatings were designed as HTDM-coated and HTD-coated samples.

The adhesion strength of coatings was evaluated using the cross-cut adhesion test (Cross Hatch Tester: Neutrek Instruments). In this test, a grid pattern of 1 mm squares was created by scratching the coated surface. After that, an adhesive tape was applied over the grid and then rapidly removed. Finally, the surface was inspected by optical microscope (Nikon SMZ 1000) to identify any adhesion failure, in accordance with ISO 2409 and ASTM 3002 standard tests.

Fig. 1. Schematic representation of MTES-modified polysilazane (HTDM) synthesis route.

Table 1

Composition of the MTES sols prepared using water and/or nitric acid.

Label	Molar ratio (H ₂ O/MTES)	H ₂ O (mmol)	MTES (mmol)	HNO ₃ (g)
HM1	0.1	0.67	6.7	–
HM2	0.8	5.36	6.7	–
HM3	0.1	0.67	6.7	0.02
HM4	0.8	5.36	6.7	0.02

The cross-section and surface morphology of coated samples were examined by Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM, Hitachi S4700, Japan, Tokyo) fitted with an EDX detector (model: Hitachi S4700). For cross-section, the samples were embedded in epoxy resin. The embedding process involved applying a vacuum to enable complete resin penetration into surface features and to remove air bubbles which helps achieve a clear artifact-free interface for later polishing. Then, samples were polished using abrasive paper (silicon carbide) and diamond powder.

Kruss DSA 100 equipment (Drop Shape Analysis; model: Kruss DSA 100) was used to measure the contact angle of coated substrates by depositing 5 μ l drop of water on the coating surface. All measurements were performed in triplicate to verify reproducibility.

The corrosion protection performance of coatings was evaluated by electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) technique using Gamry FAS2 electrochemical unit (Gamry, United Kingdom, Warminster) with an AC signal. A saturated calomel electrode (SCE), a platinum wire, and the coated/uncoated stainless steel substrate were employed as reference, counter, and working electrode, respectively. The measurements were conducted in a 3.5 wt% NaCl electrolyte solution considering an exposed area of 0.78 cm². The open circuit potential (E_{ocp}) was recorded for 3600 s to reach a steady state condition before performing EIS tests. EIS measurements were carried out over a frequency range of 200,000–0.01 Hz, applying a sinusoidal amplitude of 10 mV. The reproducibility of measurements was verified by taking three separate

measurements for each sample. The electrochemical parameters were determined through averaging three measurements and the corresponding curve was selected for figure presentation.

The chemical resistance of the HTDM-coated sample was evaluated following the procedure described in paper [21], by applying water droplets containing 5 wt% NaOH, 0.5 M CuSO₄ and 5 wt% H₂SO₄, by visually examining the surface after 12 h of exposure at room temperature. To assess self-cleaning behaviour against common beverages, the coated samples were immersed in skimmed milk, coffee with milk, coke, and orange juice for 1 min. The coated samples were then slowly withdrawn at 10 cm/min and visually examined.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Synthesis and characterization of MTES-modified polysilazane

The first step of the synthesis, involving the partial hydrolysis of MTES by adding water and/or nitric acid, was investigated using FTIR. Fig. 2a shows the FTIR spectra of liquid HM1, HM2, HM3, and HM4 samples, compared with the spectrum of the MTES precursor. The enlarged views of the region of interest in the wavenumber ranges of 1500–400 cm⁻¹ and 4000–2500 cm⁻¹ are also provided in Fig. 2b and c, respectively. Characteristic absorption bands at 777 cm⁻¹, 818 cm⁻¹, 956 cm⁻¹, 1074 cm⁻¹, and 1100 cm⁻¹ attributed to Si-O-CH₃ stretching vibrations of the methoxy groups in the MTES precursor were identified in Fig. 2a [26]. Theoretically, the relative intensity of these bands provides information about the extent of the hydrolysis and subsequent condensation reaction of MTES. As shown in the FTIR spectra of HM1, and HM2 sols, the intensity of the Si-O-CH₃ bands exhibits no significant changes compared to the MTES precursors, indicating that the hydrolysis reaction of the MTES molecule is not promoted by the addition of water alone. This observation is in good agreement with previous studies, which indicate that water, in the absence of an acid catalyst, is insufficient to initiate the hydrolysis process in a significant manner [26,27]. Consequently, significant differences are observed in the FTIR

Fig. 2. FTIR spectra of HM1, HM2, HM3, and HM4 sols and their comparison to MTES precursor in the spectral ranges of a) 4000–400 cm^{-1} , b) 1500–400 cm^{-1} and c) 4000–2500 cm^{-1} .

spectra of HM3 and HM4 sols compared to MTES precursor. In both spectra, a decrease in the intensity of the Si-O-CH₃ bands was observed along with the rise of a new peak at 870 cm^{-1} , corresponding to the stretching vibration of Si-OH (silanol) groups [28]. These findings indicate that the hydrolysis reaction of the methoxy groups of MTES occurred in both sols. It is important to note, as suggested by Furtat et al. [16], that the presence of -OH groups in the hydrolyzed MTES is essential for its successful incorporation into the Durazane 1800 backbone. The -OH groups of the hydrolyzed species can easily react with the reactive Si-H bonds of the silazane backbone via a dehydrogenation reaction, provided the reaction is catalyzed by TBAF. However, an appropriate selection should be made between HM3 and HM4 before their incorporation in the Durazane 1800 backbone, as an excessive concentration of -OH groups can trigger the degradation of the silazane backbone. Furtat et al. [16] have shown that an excess of hydroxyl (OH) groups leads to the formation of low molecular weight polymers, associated with the cleavage of the Si-N bonds in the silazane backbone.

By comparing both spectra (HM3 and HM4), two main differences are distinguished. First, the characteristic band corresponding to the

Si-O-Si stretching vibration at 1027 cm^{-1} appears in the HM4 spectrum (Fig. 2a). Second, the intensity of the broad band around 3450–3400 cm^{-1} , associated with O-H stretching vibrations mode, is significantly higher in the HM4 sol (Fig. 2b). Such differences imply that the extent of hydrolysis and condensation reactions is greater in the HM4 sol. Not only a siloxane network (Si-O-Si) is formed in HM4 sol, but a higher amount of -OH groups is also detected, increasing the risk of degrading the silazane backbone through Si-N bond cleavage. To avoid the degradation and to ensure the effective incorporation of hydrolyzed MTES into the OPSZ structure, the HM4 sol was excluded from further experiments and only HM3 sol was selected for the following synthesis steps, due to a lower concentration of available -OH groups. This minimizes the risk of Si-N bond cleavage and helps maintain the polymer molecular weight in solution.

HM3 sol was incorporated into the Durazane 1800 backbone to obtain the MTES-modified polysilazane polymer (HTDM). Fig. 3a shows the FTIR spectra of the HTDM and HTD liquid samples after 4 h mixing at 80 °C in wavenumber ranges of 2500–500 cm^{-1} to highlight the area showing significant differences between the samples. The spectrum of the

Fig. 3. a) FTIR spectra of HTDM and HTD solutions in the range of 2500–500 cm^{-1} ; b) schematic representation of the dehydrogenation-based mechanism between Si–H and OH groups using TBAF as catalyst.

the HTD solution synthesized without MTES allows examining the effect of MTES incorporation. The characteristic absorption bands of Durazane 1800 precursor, as reported in the literature, are listed in Table 2. As illustrated in Fig. 3a, HTDM and HTD spectra show the characteristic absorption bands associated with pure Durazane 1800, including Si–H (2119 cm^{-1}), Si–NH–Si (1167 cm^{-1}), and Si–N–Si (1020 cm^{-1}). This indicates that the chemical structure of the Durazane 1800 precursor is preserved in both the HTDM and HTD solutions [26,29]. Nonetheless, a comparative analysis of the spectra reveals two main differences. First, the Si–H band at 2119 cm^{-1} becomes less intense, and a new absorption band at 1080 cm^{-1} , associated with the stretching vibration of Si–O–Si bonds, appears in the HTDM spectrum, indicating that the silanol groups (Si–OH) from the hydrolyzed MTES have reacted with Si–H groups from Durazane 1800. The formation of Si–O–Si bonds (Fig. 3b) confirms successful incorporation of MTES in the organopolysilazane backbone. Previous studies [29–31] have demonstrated that the reactivity between Si–H groups and hydroxyl-containing species is preferentially promoted in the presence of tetra-*n*-butylammonium fluoride (TBAF) as a catalyst. This reaction develops through a dehydrogenation-based mechanism, in which the Si–H bonds are initially activated by TBAF with subsequent nucleophilic attack by –OH groups. As a result, Si–O–Si bonds and hydrogen gas (H_2) are formed as byproducts. It should be noted that the vinyl groups in Durazane are predominantly unreacted at this temperature, since peroxide-initiated vinyl polymerization requires temperatures above $90 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ [32].

The presence of Si–OH groups absorption bands at 950 cm^{-1} and 829 cm^{-1} in the HTDM spectrum suggests that not all Si–OH groups were consumed during the reaction [33,34]. These unreacted groups play a role in the polymer crosslinking during the thermal curing process, contributing to an increase of the polymer network density.

FTIR analysis was also used to investigate the crosslinking behaviour

Table 2
Typical absorption bands of Durazane 1800 precursor.

Wavenumber (cm^{-1})	Vibration band/mode	Wavenumber (cm^{-1})	Vibration band/mode
3400, 3380	N–H (stretching)	2960, 3046	C–H (vinyl group)
2119	Si–H (deformation)	1403, 1593	C=C (stretching)
1250	Si–CH ₃ (deformation)	1020, 880	Si–N–Si
1167	Si–NH–Si (deformation)	784	Si–C

of MTES-modified polyorganosilazane (HTDM) during the thermal curing. The HTDM solution was heat treated at $100 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 24 h, to reproduce heat treatment used for the coating process. In addition, the same thermal heat treatment was performed for the HTD polymer and pure Durazane 1800 for comparative purposes. Fig. 4a shows the appearance of the HTDM, HTD, and Durazane 1800 samples after the heat treatment. The HTDM sample has a powdery appearance, in contrast to the gelatinous texture observed for HTD and Durazane 1800 samples, suggesting a more cross-linked structure in the HTDM sample. To corroborate this observation, FTIR analyses of all the heated samples

Fig. 4. a-b) Photograph and FTIR spectra of HTDM, HTD, and Durazane 1800 polymers cured at $100 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 24 h.

were performed. Fig. 4b displays the spectra of the cured HTDM, HTD, and Durazane 1800 polymers.

It is well established that, under ambient moisture conditions, curing of Durazane 1800 involves different reactions which affect the cross-linking of the silazane network [29,30]. Fig. 5 outlines possible reaction pathways involved in the curing process including: transamination, dehydrogenation and hydrolysis-condensation reactions. Si—H (2119 cm^{-1}) and Si—NH—Si (1167 cm^{-1}) bonds are still present in the spectrum of Durazane 1800 in Fig. 4b, indicating the polymer was not fully crosslinked. This is aligned with its gel-like appearance (Fig. 4a) and with previous studies, which report that the crosslinking reaction of organosilazane polymers is limited by steric effects caused by the presence of organic substituents such as methyl (Si—CH₃) and vinyl (C=C) chemical bonds [29,30].

The FTIR spectrum of the HTD sample is similar to that of pure Durazane 1800, with the exception of a slight decrease in the Si—H band intensity and a slight increase in the intensity of the Si—O—Si band. This suggests that some Si—H groups reacted by dehydrogenation reaction with other Si—H groups or with water molecules (Figs. 3b and 5), leading to the formation of R₃Si—SiR₃ and Si—O—Si bonds. These slight differences suggest a more cross-linked silazane network compared to pure Durazane 1800. However, the presence of unreacted Si—H (2119 cm^{-1}) and Si—NH—Si (1167 cm^{-1}) bands along with the observed gel-like appearance indicates the polymer network is not completely cross-linked, similarly to pure Durazane 1800. For coating application, and especially when thin layers (<10 μm) are required, an insufficiently cross-linked structure is an important disadvantage.

The FTIR spectrum of HTDM shows notable differences compared to HTD and pure Durazane 1800. In the HTDM spectrum (Fig. 4b), the Si—H (2119 cm^{-1}) and N—H (3352 cm^{-1}) bands disappear, and the intensity of Si—NH—Si band is significantly reduced, suggesting that these groups reacted during the curing process. This behaviour suggests the incorporation of MTES promotes the crosslinking of the silazane network significantly. The enhanced degree of crosslinking observed in the HTDM sample is attributed to the presence of silanol (Si—OH) groups derived from the hydrolyzed MTES precursor, which remain unreacted in the liquid phase (as seen in Fig. 3a). During the curing process, the Si—OH groups react with the Si—NH—Si or Si—H reactive groups through

a) Transamination

b) Dehydrogenation: (Si-H with N-H)

c) Dehydrogenation: (Si-H with Si-H)

d) Hydrolysis and polycondensation reaction of HTT in ambient atmosphere

Fig. 5. Schematic representation of the reaction pathways involved in the curing process of Durazane 1800.

hydrolysis and condensation reactions (Fig. 5), forming new Si—O—Si bonds and promoting a highly cross-linked network. The presence of a broad band at 1080 cm^{-1} in the HTDM spectrum, characteristic of Si—O—Si bonds, confirms the scenario.

To summarise, MTES is not only successfully incorporated into the silazane backbone during the synthesis but also plays a crucial role in increasing the degree of crosslinking of the organosilazane network during the curing process.

The viscosity of HTDM and HTD solutions was also measured after 6 h of aging, and similar values between 2 and 3 mPa·s were determined for both solutions. The viscosity is suitable for the preparation of homogeneous coatings by dip-coating.

3.2. Deposition and characterization of coatings

HTDM and HTD solutions were deposited on AISI 304 stainless steel by dip-coating at a withdrawal rate of 30 cm/min and then cured at 100 °C for 24 h. After the thermal curing process, homogeneous and transparent coatings were obtained, making them appropriate for practical application in many real-world scenarios.

The cross-ruling test (ISO 2409 and ASTM 3002 standard tests) was used to test HTDM and HTD coatings adhesion on the AISI 304 substrates. As shown in Fig. 6, the visual examination of the grid lines of both HTDM and HTD coatings shows no signs of failure/or delamination. Therefore, both coatings were classified as OB, demonstrating their excellent adhesion properties.

One advantage of using silazane-derived coatings lies in their ability to form a strong Metal—O—Si bond via multiple reaction pathways. As explained by Barroso et al. [18], the Metal—O—Si bond can be formed via a dehydrogenation reaction mechanism, where Si—H groups of the silazane backbone react with the —OH groups present on the substrate. Alternatively, Si—NH—Si present in the silazane backbone can also react with —OH groups on the substrate, leading to oxygen bridge formation and the release of ammonia (NH₃). Additionally, the silazane backbone can undergo hydrolysis by interaction with water molecules adsorbed on the surface of the substrate, forming Si—OH groups. These Si—OH groups can subsequently condense with the —OH groups present on the substrate

Fig. 6. The results of adherence test of a) HTDM coating, and b) HTD coating before and after removing the adhesive tape.

surface, forming covalent Metal-O-Si bonds. These multiple bonding routes between silazane-based polymer and the AISI304 stainless steel substrate are a key factor in obtaining coatings with good adhesion properties.

The surface morphology of HTDM and HTD coatings are shown in Fig. 7. SEM images of HTDM (Fig. 7a) and HTD (Fig. 7b) show in both cases a crack-free morphology. However, HTD coating contained inhomogeneous zones characterized by circular-shaped spots distributed along the surface. These irregularities are attributed to the higher Si—H bonds content in the HTD coating, identified in the FTIR spectrum (Figs. 3a, 4b). A higher amount of Si—H groups, likely associated with the dehydrogenation reaction, increases the release of hydrogen gas which affects the homogeneity of the coating. Released hydrogen gas forms bubbles in the coating, perceived as heterogeneities. Although these heterogeneities do not affect the adhesion properties of the HTD coating, they adversely affect its corrosion protection. The elemental composition of the surface of the HTD and HTDM coatings was analysed using Energy Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy (EDS) mapping. The results confirmed the presence of Si, O, C, and N in both coatings. The coating thicknesses were also evaluated from the cross-sections images shown in Fig. 8a) and b). The thickness of both coatings is approximately 5 μm .

The water contact angle (WCA) values of HTDM and HTD coated samples and the bare stainless steel substrate were measured to evaluate their surface wettability. As shown in Fig. 9, WCA of bare steel and HTD samples are below 90° , indicating a hydrophilic surface. In contrast, the WCA of the HTDM is much higher, around 104° . This improvement can be associated with two main factors. First, the absence of polar groups in the HTDM coating, such as Si—H and Si—NH—Si. Second, the incorporation of MTES introduces non-polar $-\text{CH}_3$ groups into the network, decreasing the affinity of the surface to water molecules and thus improving water-repellent behaviour. These results are in good agreement with FTIR results (Fig. 4b).

3.3. Corrosion performance of the studied coatings

Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS) measurements were carried out to investigate the corrosion performance of HTDM and HTD coatings in detail. Fig. 10 shows the Bode plots of HTDM and HTD coatings as a function of immersion time. For comparison, the EIS measurement of bare stainless steel measured after 1 h of immersion in

3.5 wt% NaCl solution is also included in Fig. 10.

Generally, the impedance spectra for HTDM and HTD coatings have higher impedance $|Z|$ values across the whole frequency range compared to bare stainless steel. The impedance modulus at low frequencies ($|Z|_{f: 0.01\text{Hz}}$) provides an estimate of the overall corrosion protection of the samples; therefore, this value was used to compare the corrosion protection of the coatings. The low frequency impedance modulus ($|Z|_{f: 0.01\text{Hz}}$) of HTDM and HTD coated samples is approximately four orders of magnitude higher than that of stainless steel after 4 weeks of immersion, indicating that both coatings act as physical barriers. However, the evolution of the impedance spectra with immersion time varies between the two coatings, highlighting their different behaviour with long-term immersions. Thus, with increasing immersion time, the impedance modulus value ($|Z|_{f: 0.01\text{Hz}}$) of the HTDM coating increases from $10^8 \Omega \cdot \text{cm}^2$ to $1.3 \times 10^9 \Omega \cdot \text{cm}^2$ after 4 weeks, whereas the $|Z|_{f: 0.01\text{Hz}}$ value of HTD coating remains unchanged. In addition, the phase angle of the HTDM coating at high frequency range ($f: 10^3$ – 10^5 Hz) stays close to -90° , displaying a broader and more defined phase angle plateau over time compared to HTD coating. The gradual increase in impedance modulus at low frequency and the sustained phase angle response of -90° at high frequency for the HTDM coating reveal its superior barrier performance and more stable capacitive behaviour compared to the HTD sample.

To assess the electrochemical processes occurring at the electrolyte/film/metal interface of the samples, the EIS data were fitted using electrical equivalent circuits (EC), as presented in Fig. 11. Table 3 shows the fitted values obtained for the different spectra over immersion time. The total corrosion resistance (R_p) values were calculated as the sum of all the faradaic resistances according to the fitted values given in Table 3.

In general, these equivalent circuits are based on the combination of resistance and capacitance elements which represent the aging process of the coatings [35]. The CPE behaviour is generally attributed to a distribution of time constant and is given by the following equation (Eq. (1))

$$Z_{\text{CPE}} = \frac{1}{Y_0(j\omega)^n} \quad (1)$$

where (Y_0) is the pseudocapacitance and n is the CPE exponent (which

Fig. 7. The SEM images and EDX elemental mapping of the (a) HTDM and (b) HTD coatings.

Fig. 8. The cross-section SEM images of (a) HTDM and (b) HTD coatings.

Fig. 9. The water droplet contact angle of 1) stainless steel, 2) HTD coating, 3) HTDM coating.

represents the deviation from the ideal behaviour and varies between 0 and 1) [25,36,37].

During the first 48 h of immersion, an equivalent circuit with two-time-constant is required to fit the HTD and HTDM spectra. In this case, R_s corresponds to the resistance of the electrolyte solution, while (R_c) and (CPE_c) correspond to the resistance and the constant phase element of the coating. In contrast, (R_{ox}) and (CPE_{ox}) can be attributed to a passive oxide film [35,38–40]. The presence of the second time constant indicates that both coatings exhibit a certain degree of porosity [41]. Although the HTDM coating shows a more homogeneous morphology and a highly cross-linked structure compared to HTD, it may still contain partially polymerized regions that evolve into small pores. These pores facilitate the electrolyte penetration through the coating, promoting the formation of a passive CrO_3 layer at the substrate/coating interface [37,42,43]. However, it should be emphasized that at this immersion time (48 h), the resistance of HTDM coating ($6.1 \times 10^7 \Omega\text{-cm}^2$) is one order of magnitude higher than that of HTD ($5.5 \times 10^6 \Omega\text{-cm}^2$), demonstrating the superior barrier performance of the HTDM coating from the initial stage of immersion.

As the immersion time increases up to 4 weeks, a three-time constant EC is required to introduce for fitting the spectrum of HTD sample, suggesting the presence of an additional interfacial process. In this case, the additional third-time constant element (R_{ct} and CPE_{dl}) corresponds to the charge transfer resistance and the electrical double-layer capacitance between the film/substrate interface. This new contribution is associated with the electrochemical activity of the substrate through the pores, resulting from the progressive formation of pathways along the coating over time [44]. The significant amount of reactive groups (Si–H and Si–NH–Si) in the network, as was demonstrated by FTIR (Fig. 4b) can react with water when exposed to electrolyte, causing the formation of

Si–OH groups and fragmentation of the structure of the coating, reducing the barrier properties. As the exposure time increases, the electrolyte penetrates deeper, reaching the metal/coating interface. Table 3 shows that the resistance values of the HTD coating (R_c) and the oxide layer (R_{ox}) decrease from $5.5 \times 10^6 \Omega\text{-cm}^2$ and $2.3 \times 10^8 \Omega\text{-cm}^2$ to $9.2 \times 10^3 \Omega\text{-cm}^2$ and $1.3 \times 10^4 \Omega\text{-cm}^2$, respectively. This decrease confirms the loss of protective integrity of the HTD coating and its passive oxide layer during prolonged immersion.

In contrast, a longer immersion time for the HTDM sample does not change the number of time constants, suggesting that the higher degree of cross-linking hinders or delays charge transfer processes at the interface. In this case, the resistance of the oxide layer is observed to increase from $1.5 \times 10^7 \Omega\text{-cm}^2$ to $6.4 \times 10^8 \Omega\text{-cm}^2$ due to the inherent passive properties of chromium species in the substrate. The increase in the resistance of the chromium oxide layer with immersion time enhances the protective character of the system by limiting the movement of corrosive ions through the coating. As a result, the overall polarization resistance (R_p) also increases in two orders of magnitude, reflecting the improved barrier performance and the self-passivating behaviour of the HTDM system with immersion.

It can be thus concluded that the highly cross-linked HTDM coating, achieved through the incorporation of MTES, provides more effective corrosion protection for longer immersion times than HTD.

The digital images of the HTD and HTDM coating samples before and after EIS measurement are provided in Fig. 12.

The visual inspection after 4 weeks of immersion clearly shows that the HTD sample exhibits a surface discoloration, clearly indicating the breakdown of the film. In contrast, the HTDM sample maintains a bright appearance, confirming the absence of deterioration and supporting the electrochemical results.

In daily life, surfaces are often exposed to different kinds of contamination and corrosive environments, so coatings with self-cleaning properties and good chemical resistance are important. The chemical resistance of the HTDM coating was evaluated by exposing coated surfaces to various corrosive solutions (5 wt% NaOH, 0.5 M $CuSO_4$ and 5 wt% H_2SO_4) for 12 h (Fig. 13a). The contact angle of each solution was measured to assess the wettability (Fig. 13b).

The contact angles of all corrosive solutions on the HTDM coating are approximately 80° (Fig. 13b), which is lower than that measured in water (Fig. 9). However, no visible stains or degradation were observed in the coated region exposed to 0.5 M $CuSO_4$ and 5 wt% H_2SO_4 solutions, indicating strong chemical resistance against acidic and oxidative agents. Slight deterioration was observed in the area exposed to 5 wt% NaOH solution. This could be attributed to a highly reactive nature of OH^- ions, which can attack both the Si–O–Si and Si–N–Si bonds compromising the integrity of the coating in an alkaline environment.

Finally, the self-cleaning performance of the HTDM coating was tested by visually inspecting the surface after immersion in commonly consumed beverages, such as skimmed milk, orange juice, cola, and coffee with milk (Fig. 13c). No visual liquid residues were observed on the HTDM surface after immersion in skimmed milk and orange juice. Minor traces were observed after coke and coffee-milk immersion,

Fig. 10. Impedance modulus and phase angle diagrams of the (a) HTDM and (b) HTD coated samples immersed in 3.5 % NaCl solution at different immersion times.

Fig. 11. (a) two-time constant and (b) three-time constant equivalent circuit models.

probably due to the high content of gas in the coke and the high content of fat in the milk. Despite these minor residues, HTDM coating has suitable self-cleaning properties for some liquids.

In summary, HTDM coating has demonstrated strong potential to improve the corrosion protection of metal substrates against sodium chloride-induced corrosion, while also offering suitable chemical resistance and self-cleaning properties. These combined functionalities improve the long-term durability of the coated surfaces reducing the

inconvenience of maintenance cost and cleaning efforts.

4. Conclusion

Methyltriethoxysilane (MTES) was successfully incorporated into a polysilazane structure (Durazane 1800) via a sol-gel method, using tetrabutylammonium fluoride (TBAF) as the catalyst. The pre-hydrolysis of MTES played an important role in the preparation of polysilazane-based hybrid complex, since the presence of a sufficient number of -OH groups allowed the formation of covalent bond between MTES and the polysilazane backbone. During the thermal curing, an organo-silazane network with a high crosslinking density was formed, which significantly improved the structural integrity of the coating. This directly influenced the improvement properties. The MTES-modified polysilazane (HTDM) coating showed excellent adhesion to the steel substrate (AISI304), remarkable hydrophobicity (contact angle of $\sim 104^\circ$), and good corrosion protection in aggressive chloride environment, compared to unmodified polysilazane coating (HTD). Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS) results confirmed the increased corrosion protection of the HTDM coating in comparison with HTD. The

Table 3

The calculated EIS parameters derived from fitting the EIS results with equivalent circuit model. The fitting result has a lower chi-square value, between 10^{-4} and 10^{-5} .

Sample	Time	R_c			CPE_c			R_{ox}			CPE_{ox}			R_{ct}			CPE_{dl}			R_p					
		$\Omega \cdot \text{cm}^2$	Y_0	n	$\Omega \cdot \text{cm}^2$	Y_0	n	$\Omega \cdot \text{cm}^2$	Y_0	n	$\Omega \cdot \text{cm}^2$	Y_0	n	$\Omega \cdot \text{cm}^2$	Y_0	n_{dl}	$\Omega \cdot \text{cm}^2$	Y_0	n_{dl}	$\Omega \cdot \text{cm}^2$	Y_0	n_{dl}			
HTD	48 h	5.54×10^6	1.1×10^{-9}	0.98	2.3×10^8	7.9×10^{-9}	0.72	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	2.4×10^8	–	–		
		$\pm 6.2 \times 10^4$	$\pm 7.6 \times 10^{-12}$	$\pm 6.7 \times 10^{-4}$	$\pm 1.2 \times 10^6$	$\pm 3.4 \times 10^{-11}$	$\pm 2.0 \times 10^{-3}$	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	10^8	–	–	
	1 week	2.1×10^5	9.8×10^{-10}	$0.98 \pm 1.3 \times 10^{-3}$	1.1×10^6	1.6×10^{-8}	0.85	6.4×10^8	1.1×10^{-8}	0.86	6.4×10^8	1.1×10^{-8}	0.86	1.9×10^{-8}	1.1×10^{-8}	0.83	5.5×10^8	1.1×10^{-8}	0.83	5.5×10^8	1.1×10^{-8}	0.83	5.5×10^8	1.1×10^{-8}	0.83
		$\pm 2.1 \times 10^3$	$\pm 1.5 \times 10^{-11}$	$\pm 10^{-3}$	$\pm 1.9 \times 10^5$	$\pm 2.1 \times 10^{-9}$	$\pm 1.8 \times 10^{-2}$	$\pm 7.5 \times 10^6$	$\pm 2.2 \times 10^{-9}$	$\pm 2.3 \times 10^{-2}$	$\pm 7.5 \times 10^6$	$\pm 2.2 \times 10^{-9}$	$\pm 2.3 \times 10^{-2}$	$\pm 1.8 \times 10^6$	$\pm 2.2 \times 10^{-9}$	$\pm 1.6 \times 10^{-2}$	10^8	$\pm 2.2 \times 10^{-9}$	$\pm 1.6 \times 10^{-2}$	10^8	$\pm 2.2 \times 10^{-9}$	$\pm 1.6 \times 10^{-2}$	10^8	$\pm 2.2 \times 10^{-9}$	$\pm 1.6 \times 10^{-2}$
	2 week	6.0×10^4	1.1×10^{-9}	$0.97 \pm 4.2 \times 10^{-3}$	9.5×10^6	2.2×10^{-8}	0.81	5.4×10^8	1.9×10^{-8}	0.83	5.4×10^8	1.9×10^{-8}	0.83	1.9×10^{-8}	1.9×10^{-8}	0.79	6.4×10^8	3.3×10^{-8}	0.79	6.4×10^8	3.3×10^{-8}	0.79	6.4×10^8	3.3×10^{-8}	0.79
		$\pm 1.4 \times 10^3$	$\pm 5.7 \times 10^{-11}$	$\pm 10^{-3}$	$\pm 1.1 \times 10^6$	$\pm 9.0 \times 10^{-10}$	$\pm 6.3 \times 10^{-3}$	$\pm 1.8 \times 10^7$	$\pm 9.2 \times 10^{-10}$	$\pm 1.6 \times 10^{-2}$	$\pm 1.8 \times 10^7$	$\pm 9.2 \times 10^{-10}$	$\pm 1.6 \times 10^{-2}$	$\pm 1.8 \times 10^7$	$\pm 9.2 \times 10^{-10}$	$\pm 1.6 \times 10^{-2}$	10^8	$\pm 9.2 \times 10^{-10}$	$\pm 1.6 \times 10^{-2}$	10^8	$\pm 9.2 \times 10^{-10}$	$\pm 1.6 \times 10^{-2}$	10^8	$\pm 9.2 \times 10^{-10}$	$\pm 1.6 \times 10^{-2}$
	3 week	2.2×10^4	1.1×10^{-9}	$0.97 \pm 2.5 \times 10^{-3}$	3.0×10^4	2.1×10^{-8}	0.90	6.4×10^8	3.3×10^{-8}	0.79	6.4×10^8	3.3×10^{-8}	0.79	6.4×10^8	3.3×10^{-8}	0.79	6.4×10^8	3.3×10^{-8}	0.79	6.4×10^8	3.3×10^{-8}	0.79	6.4×10^8	3.3×10^{-8}	0.79
		$\pm 2.3 \times 10^2$	$\pm 3.6 \times 10^{-11}$	$\pm 10^{-3}$	$\pm 4.8 \times 10^3$	$\pm 2.5 \times 10^{-9}$	$\pm 1.1 \times 10^{-2}$	$\pm 1.6 \times 10^7$	$\pm 2.5 \times 10^{-9}$	$\pm 3.6 \times 10^{-3}$	$\pm 1.6 \times 10^7$	$\pm 2.5 \times 10^{-9}$	$\pm 3.6 \times 10^{-3}$	$\pm 1.6 \times 10^7$	$\pm 2.5 \times 10^{-9}$	$\pm 3.6 \times 10^{-3}$	10^8	$\pm 2.5 \times 10^{-9}$	$\pm 3.6 \times 10^{-3}$	10^8	$\pm 2.5 \times 10^{-9}$	$\pm 3.6 \times 10^{-3}$	10^8	$\pm 2.5 \times 10^{-9}$	$\pm 3.6 \times 10^{-3}$
	4 week	9.2×10^3	8.9×10^{-10}	$0.99 \pm 5.9 \times 10^{-3}$	1.3×10^4	4.6×10^{-8}	0.82	6.8×10^8	9.7×10^{-9}	1	6.8×10^8	9.7×10^{-9}	1	9.7×10^{-9}	9.7×10^{-9}	1	6.8×10^8	9.7×10^{-9}	1	6.8×10^8	9.7×10^{-9}	1	6.8×10^8	9.7×10^{-9}	1
		$\pm 1.7 \times 10^2$	$\pm 7.1 \times 10^{-11}$	$\pm 10^{-3}$	$\pm 9.1 \times 10^2$	$\pm 5.8 \times 10^{-10}$	$\pm 3.5 \times 10^{-3}$	$\pm 3.2 \times 10^7$	$\pm 5.6 \times 10^{-10}$	–	$\pm 3.2 \times 10^7$	$\pm 5.6 \times 10^{-10}$	–	$\pm 3.2 \times 10^7$	$\pm 5.6 \times 10^{-10}$	–	10^8	$\pm 5.6 \times 10^{-10}$	–	10^8	$\pm 5.6 \times 10^{-10}$	–	10^8	$\pm 5.6 \times 10^{-10}$	–
	HTDM	48 h	6.1×10^7	2.6×10^{-9}	$0.95 \pm 8.6 \times 10^{-4}$	1.5×10^7	4.5×10^{-8}	0.72	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	7.7×10^7	–	–	
			$\pm 1.9 \times 10^6$	$\pm 2.1 \times 10^{-11}$	$\pm 10^{-4}$	$\pm 2.5 \times 10^6$	$\pm 1.3 \times 10^{-8}$	$\pm 9.9 \times 10^{-2}$	$\pm 9.9 \times 10^{-2}$	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	10^7	–	–
1 week		1.5×10^8	2.5×10^{-9}	$0.95 \pm 6.3 \times 10^{-4}$	2.2×10^7	3.1×10^{-8}	0.94	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	1.7×10^8	–	–	
		$\pm 3.6 \times 10^6$	$\pm 1.5 \times 10^{-11}$	$\pm 10^{-4}$	$\pm 4.1 \times 10^6$	$\pm 9.6 \times 10^{-9}$	$\pm 1.1 \times 10^{-1}$	$\pm 1.1 \times 10^{-1}$	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	10^8	–	–	
2 week		8.1×10^8	2.3×10^{-9}	$0.96 \pm 5.0 \times 10^{-4}$	1.3×10^8	2.9×10^{-8}	0.86	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	9.4×10^8	–	–	
		$\pm 1.9 \times 10^7$	$\pm 9.9 \times 10^{-12}$	$\pm 10^{-4}$	$\pm 3.1 \times 10^7$	$\pm 1.7 \times 10^{-8}$	$\pm 1.6 \times 10^{-1}$	$\pm 1.6 \times 10^{-1}$	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	10^8	–	–	
3 week		5.6×10^7	2.4×10^{-9}	$0.95 \pm 1.1 \times 10^{-3}$	1.9×10^9	3.8×10^{-10}	0.72	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	1.9×10^9	–	–	
		$\pm 2.6 \times 10^7$	$\pm 2.8 \times 10^{-11}$	$\pm 10^{-3}$	$\pm 3.6 \times 10^7$	$\pm 2.5 \times 10^{-11}$	$\pm 1.9 \times 10^{-2}$	$\pm 1.9 \times 10^{-2}$	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	10^9	–	–	
4 week		9.8×10^8	2.4×10^{-9}	$0.95 \pm 4.1 \times 10^{-4}$	6.4×10^8	4.51×10^{-9}	0.54	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	1.6×10^9	–	–	
		$\pm 7.0 \times 10^7$	$\pm 8.6 \times 10^{-12}$	$\pm 10^{-4}$	$\pm 1.5 \times 10^8$	$\pm 2.0 \times 10^{-9}$	$\pm 1.1 \times 10^{-1}$	$\pm 1.1 \times 10^{-1}$	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	10^9	–	–	

Fig. 12. The digital images of the coated samples before and after EIS measurements.

HTDM coating showed an increase in impedance modulus ($|Z|_{0.01\text{Hz}}$) and polarization resistance (R_p) over immersion time, indicating increased barrier properties and self-passivating behaviour. In contrast, HTD showed a decrease in resistance due to structural degradation and electrolyte diffusion. The higher cross-linking density in HTDM, as a result of incorporation of MTES, effectively prevented charge transfer and maintained long-term protective performance.

Furthermore, HTDM coating showed suitable chemical resistance against acidic and oxidative environments and favourable self-cleaning

properties, making it a promising candidate for multifunctional protective coatings.

In summary, the preparation of HTDM coating from a sol-gel-modified polysilazane precursor is a promising approach for the preparation of high-performance protective coatings. It offers an effective route to overcome the limitations inherent of the use of pure polysilazanes, and improve the durability of metallic substrates in corrosive environments.

Fig. 13. Chemical corrosion resistance and self-cleaning tests carried out on HTDM coated sample a) photograph of the HTDM sample after dropping 5 μ l of each corrosive solution in the coated and uncoated area of the sample. b) Contact angle of 5 wt% NaOH, 0.5 M CuSO₄, and 5 wt% H₂SO₄ solution tested on the HTDM coated sample, c) photographs of HTDM coated samples after immersion in common beverages.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Parisa Naghadian Moghaddam: Writing – original draft, Methodology, Formal analysis. **Emilia Merino:** Writing – original draft, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Alicia Duran:** Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition. **Dusan Galusek:** Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition. **Amirhossein Pakseresht:** Writing – original draft, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis. **Milan Parchovianský:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision. **Yolanda Castro:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

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